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A **Sessão Internacional** é realizada pela **Superintendência de Relações Internacionais** com o objetivo de dar oportunidade aos estudantes de vivenciarem a experiência de apresentar trabalhos em inglês. A intenção é que os alunos se sintam motivados a participar de eventos internacionais. Ao apresentar a pesquisa em outras línguas nesse tipo de evento, há visibilidade nacional e internacional para o trabalho e para a instituição. A ação abre portas para colaborações científicas, por exemplo. A quinta edição da Sessão Internacional foi parte da programação do X Café Internacional da UEMA.

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**THE EFFECTS OF WORLD WAR II ON FASHION: Transformations, Restrictions,
and New Trends**

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INTRODUCTION

The Second World War brought significant changes to fashion, both as a reflection and as an agent of social transformation. The period was marked by material shortages, technological advancements, and shifts in gender roles, which reshaped clothing design and consumption. While Europe faced scarcity and isolation, the United States took the lead in creating its own identity, promoting sportswear as the foundation of its aesthetic. In the post-war era, fashion continued to evolve, mirroring the political and economic changes of the 20th century. This study explores the conflict's impacts on women's clothing, geographic influences, and the consolidation of American fashion, while analyzing its evolution as a reflection of social transformations.

METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted through an exploratory bibliographic review of sources addressing the history of fashion and cultural studies. A qualitative approach allowed for the examination of the war's impact on fashion from various perspectives: material, social, political, and cultural. Emblematic cases were highlighted, such as the role of haute couture in Paris and the development of the "American Look." Additionally, movements and changes following the conflict were analyzed to understand the war's ongoing influence on 20th-century fashion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

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World War II brought significant changes for women, particularly regarding work and fashion. With women entering the traditionally male-dominated sectors like industry and agriculture, there was a growing need for more practical and functional clothing, leading to the popularization of trousers and uniforms. These changes reflected the evolution of gender roles and the increasing social and economic independence of women.

Fashion faced challenges due to material shortages, as wool and silk were redirected to the war effort, prompting the adoption of synthetic fabrics like rayon. Designs became simpler and more utilitarian, featuring straight cuts and functional lines that symbolized women's adaptability and resilience. The creativity and simplicity of wartime clothing represented women's response to the restrictions of the period.

While men fought on the frontlines, women used simple accessories like scarves and costume jewelry to express optimism and resistance without sacrificing elegance. Military elements, such as structured cuts and defined shoulders, were incorporated into women's fashion, highlighting strength and authority. These elements symbolized the crucial role women played in society during the war.

The war redefined femininity, solidifying practical styles that proved women could be both elegant and functional. This transformation influenced their reintegration into the workforce after the conflict and fueled feminist movements. Thus, World War II fashion became a symbol of gender equality, reflecting societal changes and reinforcing fashion as a tool for identity and adaptation.

GLOBAL FASHION TRANSFORMATIONS DURING AND AFTER WWII: GEOGRAPHICAL INFLUENCES AND CULTURAL INTEGRATION

During and after World War II, geography and cultural exchanges played pivotal roles in shaping global fashion trends. In Europe, fabric shortages and isolation led to minimalist designs, while the United States, unaffected by the war's devastation, developed a distinct fashion identity focused on practicality and simplicity. Designers like Claire McCardell

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introduced styles such as jersey dresses and two-piece sets, which resonated with the evolving roles of women during the war. As France, the former leader in haute couture, struggled, American fashion flourished.

Technological advancements and mass production further accelerated the rise of American fashion. The use of synthetic fabrics like nylon made clothing more affordable, and the popularity of sportswear prioritized functionality over formality. This democratization of fashion represented a shift away from formal European styles and solidified American influence. Post-war, designers such as Bonnie Cashin and Anne Klein continued this trend, and the global adoption of jeans highlighted the lasting impact of American culture on fashion norms.

In Korea, World War II also reshaped fashion. Korea, especially during the era of its ancient dynasties was characterized as a relatively isolated country. However, this did not negate the fact that it had always been in contact with other cultures: it was invaded by Mongol peoples and situated between China and Japan throughout its history.

During Japanese imperial rule, Korean women were forced to adopt not only Japanese styles, but to change their names and ways to live, because the imperialist ideology of Japan obliged them so. But the end of the war brought Imperial Japan down, and, as a consequence, the country left Korea to be divided between the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics and the U.S., that brought the division of Korea and consequently, western influences, particularly from the U.S. and the affluent women known as “Shinjas,” who had studied abroad, helped integrate Western fashion into Korean culture. The U.S.-occupied region embraced American ideals and aesthetics, further blending Korean and Western styles in clothing and beauty.

World War II catalyzed a global cultural integration in fashion, with regional adaptations reflecting broader cultural exchanges. Europe’s minimalist designs contrasted with the American emphasis on practicality and innovation, while Western influences extended to regions that seemed so difficult to reach like Korea. These trends highlighted how the war facilitated a more interconnected and globalized fashion identity..

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THE EVOLUTION OF FASHION AS A MIRROR OF SOCIAL AND POLITICAL CHANGES IN THE 20TH CENTURY

Throughout the 20th century, fashion reflected social and political transformations, translating the values and challenges of each decade into clothing styles. From the early-century transition from haute couture to prêt-à-porter to the democratization and global accessibility by the century's end, fashion evolved alongside society.

“Fashion as we know it is relatively new. In ancient times and the Middle Ages, clothing styles remained virtually unchanged for a century. Fashion transformations began accelerating during the Renaissance, as Western civilization discovered different cultures, customs, and attire.” (FRINGS, 2012, p. 4)

Defining moments, such as the 1920s, symbolized women's liberation, while the 1940s showcased adaptation to the austerity of wartime, with practical garments inspired by military uniforms. In the 1960s, fashion became a symbol of rebellion, with youth driving radical changes through miniskirts, synthetic fabrics, and protest messages. This decade emphasized the influence of civil and cultural movements, introducing political identity elements and ethnic references. By the 1980s, “power dressing” embodied capitalist ideals and the rise of women in the workforce, while luxury brands solidified fashion as a status symbol, marking the globalization of the fashion market.

By the century's end, fashion had democratized, with prêt-à-porter dominating the market and technology revolutionizing production and distribution. The internet enabled global access to diverse styles, uniting cultures and redefining consumption. Thus, beyond reflecting social and political changes, 20th-century fashion became an active force in shaping new cultural norms and values.

Fashion throughout the 20th century mirrored societal and political transformations, adapting to changing values and challenges. From the flapper era's liberation to wartime practicality and post-war femininity, each decade reflected evolving gender norms. Later, countercultural movements and globalized luxury redefined fashion as both a personal and political statement. The century ended with democratization and technological advancements, showcasing fashion's ability to influence and respond to global shifts in identity and values.

CONCLUSION

As a result of what had been previously discussed in the present work, it can be said that the war redefined fashion, making it a direct reflection of social, economic, and cultural changes. Women's emancipation was one of the main drivers of this transformation, leading to more functional and symbolic clothing. American fashion emerged as an independent creative force, while the post-war era brought greater cultural integration and technological innovation. As a mirror of 20th-century transformations, fashion proved to be an adaptive and resilient tool, solidifying itself as an expression of new global identities and demands.

REFERENCES

- CHOI, J.; OH, K. The Impact of the United States Fashion on Korean Fashion in 20th Century. *패션비즈니스*, v. 21, n. 3, p. 80–92, 2017.
- FRINGS, Gini Stephens. *Moda: Do Conceito ao Consumidor*. Bookman; 9ª edição. Brasil. 1 de janeiro, 2012.
- LI, P. *Japanese War Crimes*. [s.l.] Routledge, 2017.
- SIMILI, Ivana Guilherme. Educação e produção de moda na Segunda Guerra Mundial: As voluntárias da Legião Brasileira de Assistência. *Cadernos Pagu* (31), julho-dezembro de 2008:439-469. Disponível em <
<https://www.scielo.br/j/cpa/a/Stf5QwQLbNvNMhWgZtY3kmH/?format=pdf&lang=pt>>.
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